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DETERMINATION OF SPECIFIC RESISTANCE OF AN OBLIQUE SLICE (WEDGE) ON SEMICONDUCTOR WATER

Summary. The design of an installation for obtaining a wedge of silicon wafers and structures based on them using chemical etching has been developed. The modes of obtaining an oblique section (wedge) using chemical etching with a given and reproducible geometry have been worked out, and the composition of etchants has also been selected.

Key words: oblique cut (wedge), semiconductor wafers, concentration, chemical etching, electrical conductivity, etching rate, special processing, mobility.

An oblique section (wedge) can be obtained by mechanical grinding or etching. However, from the point of view of manufacturability and reproducibility of the research results conductivity, is an etching method in addition, the final preparation mechanically polished semiconductor samples are also used etching.

To the main parameters of a semiconductor material that determine the properties semiconductor devices, including resistivity. In practice, alkaline or acidic etchants are most often used for semiconductor etching. Each etchant contains an oxidizing agent (INO II O, etc.). A complexing component capable of creating field-soluble compounds (IIF, Na OII, etc.) with semiconductor atoms. In addition, components are introduced into the etchant that affect the rate of a chemical reaction (CH, COOII, Br, J, Ag, NO, K Cr O, etc.) or the rate of etching in certain crystal directions.

Note that the etching process is exothermic. Therefore, over time, the temperature of the etchant will change. Especially in slow-acting etchants. In addition, the composition of the etchant near the surface of the semiconductor and at the periphery will not be the same.

In this regard, it is necessary to work with a large (in relation to the volume of the semiconductor) volume of the etchant and with constant stirring of the latter. Thorough mixing prevents local heating of a part of the semiconductor surface.

A sample fixed on a fluoroplastic holder 2 with the help of an engine type RD 1.5.4. smoothly descended into the bath -6 with the etchant. In order to obtain the best quality of the wedge, the etchant was mixed with a stirrer driven by an engine with a RD - 0.9 gearbox using a pick and belt drive. To preserve the geometry of the samples, the reverse sides were covered with a chemical resistant varnish (XCL) The etching rate of semiconductor wafers depends on many factors, among which the etchant composition and etching temperature occupy a special place. Moreover, the etchant composition affects both the etching rate and temperatures and the quality of the etched semiconductor surface. Obtaining a wedge using etchants involves its immersion at a constant speed, which is determined by the speed and geometry of the wedge.

Figure 1. Scheme of the installation for obtaining a clip by chemical etching 1 – flint plates 2 sample holder 3 guides 4 sample motor 5 stand 6 bath with etchant 7 stirrer 8 pike-belt drive 9 motor RD-09 chemical resistant varnish (XCL)

For the etching of silicon platinum with n and p types of conductivity, the etchant compositions were tentatively taken as follows:

1. HNO + HF + CH₃COOH ratio in parts by weight 5;3;3
2. HNO + HF+ K Cr₂O ratio in parts by weight 20;20;0;04

Silicon wafers of the EKES-0.01 type were subjected to etching.

The thickness of the samples is 320 + 20 microns, with a diameter of 60 mm, KDB -0.005 with a thickness of 350 + 20 microns and with a diameter of 76 mm, 16.5 KEF 4 with a thickness of 337 + 20 microns and a diameter of 76 mm. Experiments showed that in etchant No. etching of semiconductor wafers of the KDB type - 0.005; EKES - 0.01: KEF-4 is 0.1-0.2 microns. Sec. The surface of the plate is mirror-like. However, in the vertical and horizontal directions of the

plate surface, stripes with a depth of 2-5 microns are obtained, as well as irregularities in the horizontal direction. Further experiments showed that these irregularities are associated with gas bubbles adjacent to the surface of the plate. The irregularities in the horizontal direction were removed by introducing a wetted etchant (0.01%,) which greatly reduced the surface tension. By changing the ratio of the components, in particular by increasing the amount of HF up to four values, it was possible to increase the etching rate. up to 1-2 microns / sec. At the same time, it turned out that the surface of the plate becomes more uniform, the longitudinal stripes and pits due to the emergence of dislocations have practically disappeared

It should also be noted that the abundant release of gases during etching and the introduced wetting agent lead to intense mixing of the etchant. This, in turn, contributes to the establishment of a constant etching rate over the entire sample area. Due to the emergence of dislocations.

The etching rate when using composition № 2 turned out to be in the range of 1-3 $\mu\text{m} / \text{s}$. At the same time, the surface quality was more uniform than when using etchant composition № 1.

It has been established that at etching rates of more than 2 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$, the sample surface becomes granular (rough). .To obtain a wedge, we used the composition of etchant No. 2 (no HNO b HF) (Fig. 2, 3).

Figure 2. Dependence of the thickness of the oblique section (wedge) of the obtained chemical etching on the length of the kremin plates: 1 – KDB brand kremin plate – 0.005, 2 – EKES brand kremin plate -0.01

Figure 3. Dependence of the thickness of the oblique section obtained by chemical etching on the length of the cremin epitaelous structure 16.5 KEF -4

Experimentally, by gradually increasing the concentration of K; Cr: O, an etching rate of $1 \mu\text{m} / \text{s}$, or $2 \mu\text{m} / \text{s}$, was achieved, depending on the type of semiconductor and the geometry of the clip. With the same composition of the etchant, the etching rate of KDB -0.005 was twice higher than 16.5 KEF-4 with an epitaxial layer. It follows that in order to obtain a high-quality wedge, it is necessary to experimentally select an etchant composition for each type of semiconductor that would provide an etching rate of $2 \mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$.

It should be noted that after the end of the etching process, the sample was quickly removed from the bath, washed in distilled water, and dried. To measure the resistivity of an ingot or plate, special two-probe, three-probe, and four-probe methods are used [1–6]. These measurement methods are classical. They allow you to determine the parameters both in bulk, crystals and in thin films. Among them, the four-probe method proposed by Valles is widely used 1954 [7].

The essence of the method is as follows on the flat surface of the sample, which is a semi-infinite volume bounded by a flat surface. Place four metal probe needles with a small area of contact on the same line (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Measurement of resistivity by the four-probe method with the probe in line

This method does not require the creation of ohmic contacts to the sample and allows you to measure the resistivity of samples of the most diverse shapes and sizes. Its scope extends from the evaluation of parameters in large, semiconductor headers to the determination of impurities in diffusion layers.

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